

Rice grain yield and N uptake response to urea N and proportions of total N from applied cattle manure. Ludhiana, India.

Effect of urea and cattle manure N on P and K uptake of rice and the residual effect on soil properties and wheat yield. Ludhiana, India.

	Rates of N (kg/ha)				LSD (P=0.05)
	0	60	120	180	
<i>N application to rice</i>					
Urea	14	21	25	27	5.6
Cattle manure	14	15	21	24	
<i>K uptake of rice (kg/ha)</i>					
Urea	71	129	140	155	10.2
Cattle manure	71	87	93	149	
<i>Soil organic C (%)</i>					
Urea	0.34	0.35	0.36	0.36	0.03
Cattle manure	0.34	0.35	0.39	0.41	
<i>Olsen P (kg/ha)</i>					
Urea	22	20	13	12	3.6
Cattle manure	22	18	19	21	
<i>P application to wheat</i>					
<i>Wheat grain yield (t/ha) on soil amended with cattle manure</i>					
No P	3.2	3.5	3.6	3.8	0.21
26 kg P/ha	3.6	3.8	3.8	3.9	

and 180 kg/ha) applied through urea and through cattle manure. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The cattle manure contained 1.3% total N, 0.38% total P, and had 26:1 C:N.

Cattle manure was incorporated into the soil 1 d before transplanting rice. Urea was applied in 3 equal splits at 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 5 kg Zn/ha also was applied to rice. Variety PR106 was

transplanted 24 Jun 1986.

After harvest, all plots were subdivided to accommodate 2 levels of P (0 and 26 kg/ha). Wheat was fertilized with a uniform 80 kg N and 25 kg K/ha.

Both urea and manure N increased rice grain yield and N uptake significantly (see figure). Quadratic response curves were fitted to the rice grain yield and N uptake by considering different proportions of the cattle manure N to be as good as urea N. The regression analysis showed that 45% of

the N applied as cattle manure and urea N had effects on grain yield; 40% of N as cattle manure and urea N produced similar effects on N uptake by rice. The lower values for N uptake than for grain yield suggest that cattle manure N was more efficiently translated into rice grain yield than was urea N. Both P and K uptake of rice increased significantly with the application of either urea and cattle manure N (see table). Soil organic C content increased only when cattle manure was applied at high rates.

While Olsen P decreased significantly with urea N treatments, with cattle manure it maintained its initial level. Since both organic C and Olsen P contents were higher in soil amended with cattle manure, grain yield of the following wheat crop increased significantly. At 120 and 180 kg N/ha as cattle manure applied to rice, the wheat crop did not respond to direct P application. □

Effect of soil bulk density and soil texture on root growth

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We studied root growth of rice variety H4 at different soil bulk density and soil texture levels. The soil was a sandy loam (Rhodustalf, 19% clay, 11% silt, and 70% sand) from the central region of Sri Lanka. The texture was changed by adding medium sand in a ratio of 1:5 (sand:soil).

Soils were incubated 2 wk at 12% moisture and compacted in PVC cylinders (height and diameter 0.1 m) to a height of 7.5 cm, creating 3 levels of bulk density (1.15, 1.30, and 1.45 Mg/m³).

Ten pregerminated seeds were planted in each compacted soil column and covered with 1 cm layer of the same soil. Cores were covered with polyethylene and placed randomly in a large polyethylene chamber to minimize moisture loss. Root tips which

penetrated the entire column were counted 7 d after planting and root penetration percentage calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Roots (no.) penetrating entire soil column}}{\text{Seeds (no.) planted}}$$

The length of the longest root for each plant and the dry weight of the entire root system in a core were measured.

There were significant differences in root dry weight among soil bulk density levels for each soil texture level (see table). Root length also differed except at the highest bulk density. Both root

Mean root performance at different soil bulk densities and textures. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.

Soil bulk density (Mg/m ³)	Texture	Root dry weight (mg)	Root length (cm)	Root penetration ^a (%)
1.15	Soil	20	62	30 a
1.15	Soil + sand	13	45	25 ab
1.30	Soil	30	68	20 abc
1.30	Soil + sand	16	41	18 abc
1.45	Soil	11	4 a	0 d
1.45	Soil + sand	10	4 a	0 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

dry weight and root length increased up to soil bulk density of 1.30 Mg/m³, then decreased. Root penetration decreased

with increasing soil bulk density. The addition of sand significantly decreased both root dry weight and root length. □

Poultry manure as a N source for wetland rice

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Organic N is mineralized relatively slowly under anaerobic soil conditions. We studied whether poultry manure can be used efficiently as a source of N for wetland rice.

Soil of the experimental field was a Fatehpur loam sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.27% organic C, and 0.04% total N. Poultry manure (C:N 12, 1.85% N, 1.81% P) was compared with urea at 0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Poultry manure was incorporated into the soil in the last puddling; urea was applied in 3 equal splits at 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting rice PR 106.

After the rice was harvested, soil samples were tested for organic C and available P, and wheat was grown to study the residual effect. On half of each plot, P at 0 and 26 kg/ha was applied. A uniform 80 kg N/ha as urea was applied overall.

A quadratic grain yield response of rice to urea up to 180 kg N/ha was observed (see figure). When the source of N was poultry manure, the response was linear up to 180 kg N/ha; it was

Rice grain yield response to application of N through urea and poultry manure in Ludhiana, India.

Residual effect on wheat of poultry manure applied to rice in Ludhiana, India.

	Urea or poultry manure applied to rice as kg N/ha			
	0	60 kg	120 kg	180 kg
<i>Soil organic C (%)</i>				
Urea	0.27	0.28	0.28	0.29
Poultry manure	0.27	0.29	0.28	0.30
LSD (P=0.05)			0.02	
<i>Olsen's available P (kg/ha)</i>				
Urea	7.5	9.9	8.7	8.7
Poultry manure	7.5	10.8	14.2	12.8
LSD (P=0.05)			2.2	
<i>Wheat yield (t/ha) with P applied to poultry manure-amended plots</i>				
No P	2.95	3.33	3.49	3.63
26 kg P/ha	3.55	3.68	3.70	3.77
LSD (P=0.05)			0.19	